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THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ORGANIC ACIDS ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF MAGNESIUM HYDRIDE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of organic acids such as acetic acid, citric acid and oxalic acid and their concentration in aqueous solutions on the hydrolysis of magnesium hydride (MgH₂) has been investigated. The hydrolysis of MgH₂ was performed in a hydrogen generation reactor operated in a batch mode where the temperature and H₂ flow rate were logged. Different organic acid concentration of 1, 2, and 3 wt. % was used to study the effect on the hydrolysis of MgH₂. The hydrogen generation results indicate that the addition of organic acids to the aqueous solution increases the rate of H₂ generation as it limits the formation of the Mg(OH)₂ passivation layer. The increase in the concentration of the organic acid solutions leads to the increase in the rate and generation of H₂ via hydrolysis of MgH₂. The organic acid with the fastest hydrogen generation rate is oxalic acid, acetic acid and then citric acid. The pH before and after hydrolysis was recorded and showed that the addition of organic acids suppress the formation of Mg(OH)₂ passivation layer causing the aqueous solution to be more acidic which leads to less OH⁻ being formed during hydrolysis in the solution.

Keywords: Hydrolysis, Hydrogen generation, MgH₂, Organic acids

INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen as energy carrier is one of the most promising solutions to address the energy and environment issues and to meet future energy needs. Energy systems based on hydrogen fuel cells are characterised by high efficiency and power density and presently used in a number of stationary, portable and vehicle applications [1,2]. However, the main issue that hinders further implementation of hydrogen fuel cell technologies is compact, safe and efficient hydrogen storage. In recent years, special attention of researchers and engineers has focused on the on-board generation of hydrogen by the hydrolysis of various lightweight materials like ammonia borane, NH₃BH₃, sodium borohydride, NaBH₄, aluminium, Al, magnesium hydride, MgH₂, and so on. These materials can undergo hydrolysis at near-ambient conditions, in alkaline or acidic medium. Potentially, they can be used for efficient generation of hydrogen on-board thus mitigating the hydrogen storage challenge. Their practical implementation, however, requires solution of a number of problems including; (i) suppression of side reactions (particularly dangerous for the boron-containing compounds when a toxic diborane can appear), (ii) improvement of reaction kinetics and, at the same time, (iii) possibility to control H₂ release depending on the fuel cell need. Therefore, looking for a cheap and practical technology to generate hydrogen remains a keen focus of research all over the world.

Magnesium is an inexpensive and readily available metal, which is abundant in the earth's crust (2.4 %) and not harmful on the environment making it a suitable candidate for high-quality hydrogen generation material. Magnesium hydride readily oxidized when it comes in contact with water to form Mg(OH)₂ accompanied by H₂ gas evolution. Hydrogen is generated by hydrolysis of MgH₂ according to equation 1.

Hydrolysis of MgH₂ has a high theoretical hydrogen yield, 15.2 wt.% and 6.4 wt.% without and with accounting the weight of water, respectively. This is almost double than the amount of H₂ generated by hydrolysis of individual Mg.

Though the hydrolysis of MgH₂ occurs immediately when in contact with water but it is interrupted because of the formation of a passive magnesium hydroxide layer, which prevents the diffusion of the water to the particle inside, therefore the hydrolysis reaction is quickly stagnates. To improve the hydrolysis efficiency and the reaction rate of MgH₂, the main methods employed were carrying out the process in acidic medium [6], alloying with other metals [7], addition of chlorides [8] or ammonium salts [9], ball milling [Error! Reference source not found.], addition of graphite [Error! Reference source not found.], as well as ultra-sonication [Error! Reference source not found.]. The above-mentioned methods are all actively investigated and have been shown to enhance hydrogen generation during the hydrolysis of MgH₂. The crucial issue relating to hydrolysis of MgH₂ remains the avoidance of the barrier of hydroxide layer formation during the hydrolysis process to realize complete hydrolysis. The present work is aimed at studying the effect of organic acids such as acetic, citric and oxalic acids, which potentially have a smaller

environmental impact than that of mineral acids on the hydrolysis of MgH_2 by limiting the $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ passivation layer to enhance the hydrolysis rate and hydrogen generation yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MgH_2 powder 99.8% purity (Rockwood Lithium Germany) with average particle size of $50 \mu\text{m}$ was used as the substrate for hydrogen storage media. Different organic acids, acetic acid 99.8 %, citric acid 99.5 % and oxalic acid 99.5% purity (Alfa Aesar), were used to increase the rate of hydrogen generation. The investigation of the influence of different concentrations of organic acids (1 wt. %, 2 wt. % and 3 wt. %) on the hydrolysis rate and hydrogen generation was performed.

The hydrogen generation set-up consists of a three-neck round bottom flask that serves as the reaction vessel, thermostatic regulated water bath, the moisture absorbent unit, the flow meter (Bronkhorst 1 NL/min) and the data logger. The hydrolysis reaction of MgH_2 ($m=200 \text{ mg}$, theoretical H_2 generation after complete hydrolysis 0.34 NL) with different organic acids was carried out in a 250 ml round bottom flask with three openings, one for water/organic acid addition, one for hydrogen exhausting and one for inserting the thermocouple. The reaction flask was submerged in a thermostat. Hydrolysis reaction was initiated by quick pouring of the acid solution (50 mL) in the reaction flask. The generated hydrogen was passed through a moisture absorbent before entrance to the flow meter. The pH of the solutions before and after hydrolysis were recorded using a Metrohm 827 pH meter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the hydrolysis performance of MgH_2 with different organic acids such as acetic, citric and oxalic acid at different concentrations 1, 2 and 3 wt. %. It can be observed that hydrogen generation from MgH_2 in deionized water is extremely slow: only 0.048 NL H_2 released after 10 minutes, this was expected due to the formation of the $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ passive layer on the surface of the unreacted MgH_2 . In contrast, the addition of organic acids considerably improves the hydrogen generation of MgH_2 . In all cases both the rate and degree of hydrogen generation increased with higher concentrations of organic acids shown in figure 1 (A), (B) and (C); for the acids concentration of 3 wt. %, 100% hydrogen yield is achieved in 3–5 minutes after reaction started. From figure 1 (D) it is shown that the organic acid with the fastest hydrogen generation rate is oxalic acid, followed by acetic acid and then citric acid.

Figure 1. Hydrogen generation curves of MgH_2 at $T=20^\circ\text{C}$ in different concentration of organic acids 1, 2 and 3 wt. %, (A) Acetic Acid, (B) Citric Acid, (C) Oxalic Acid, (D) Hydrogen generation of MgH_2 in 3 wt. % organic acid solutions.

The hydrolysis of MgH_2 , leads to an increase in the pH of the reaction solution, this is due to the release of OH^- as a result causing the formation of the $Mg(OH)_2$ passive layer on the surface of MgH_2 . This is a major problem with generating hydrogen by MgH_2 hydrolysis. From Table 1 it can be observed that the hydrolysis of MgH_2 in deionized water the pH increased drastically, which is expected due to the $Mg(OH)_2$ passive layer being formed. The addition of organic acids however suppress the formation of $Mg(OH)_2$ this was mainly due to the initial pH becoming acidic which causes less OH^- to be released into the solution. It can be seen that the samples with the lowest pH after hydrolysis have the fastest rate and amount of hydrogen generated, which was oxalic acid, acetic acid then citric acid the same as the hydrogen generation results

Table 1. pH of MgH_2 solution before and after hydrolysis

	Deionized Water	Acetic Acid			Citric Acid			Oxalic Acid		
Concentration		1 wt. %	2wt. %	3wt. %	1 wt. %	2 wt. %	3wt. %	1 wt. %	2 wt. %	3 wt. %
Initial pH	6.55	2.95	2.81	2.69	2.43	2.25	2.16	1.53	1.32	1.21
Final pH	11.04	5.54	5.28	4.28	5.32	4.98	4.53	4.84	3.32	2.11

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of organic acids such as acetic, citric and oxalic acid on the hydrolysis of MgH_2 at various concentration on hydrogen generation were evaluated experimentally. The main results are shown below.

- The hydrogen generation was considerably improved by using organic acid solution instead of only deionized water, this is due to the organic acid dissolving the $Mg(OH)_2$ passivation layer.
- By increase the concentration of the organic acid solutions, the rate of hydrogen generation and amount increased as well, the organic acid with the fastest hydrogen generation rate is oxalic acid, followed by acetic acid and then citric acid. For all the acids applied, at the acid concentration of 3 wt. %, 100% H_2 yield was observed after 3–5 minutes after starting the hydrolysis reaction.
- The addition of organic acids to the hydrolysis solution caused the solution to be acidic, therefore during hydrolysis of MgH_2 in the acidic solution causes less OH^- to be released into the solution and in-turn limiting the formation of the $Mg(OH)_2$ passivation layer.

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